

Development of an advanced clothing moisture model

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Introduction

Basic clothing models used in common thermophysiology models account for sweat evaporation at the skin based on the bulk evaporative resistance of a layered clothing stack [1][2]. However, such models do not typically consider the layer-to-layer transport of vapour within the clothing ensemble. Under certain conditions, water vapour diffusing through clothing layers can reach its dew point, which results in a phase change. The evaporation and condensation of moisture within the fabric layers can have a significant impact on clothing temperature [3] and, ultimately, affect thermo-physiological response and thermal comfort perception [4]. Humans may be operating with wet clothing due to sweating, immersion or precipitation. Development of an advanced clothing moisture model that considers the storage of liquid water and the diffusion of water vapour within the fabric layers can improve the accuracy of human thermal predictions in scenarios where clothing-based condensation and evaporation occur.

Methods

A commercial heat transfer CAE software tool (TAITherm[®], ThermoAnalytics, Inc.) was modified to consider the transport of vapour and the storage of vapour and liquid moisture within a clothing ensemble. TAITherm[®] is a general thermal solver capable of modelling combined conduction, convection, radiation, and advection heat transport processes under transient or steady-state conditions. Solutions are obtained by finding temperatures that produce simultaneous energy balances on a network of thermal nodes.

For portions of the domain having a moisture component, a moisture node is created coincident with the thermal node for that location. Just as a thermal node represents the temperature at a location, a moisture node represents the mass of moisture present at the location. The initial implementation considered the presence of liquid and vapour, but only the transport of vapour, for which the metric is the humidity ratio, defined as the ratio of the mass of water vapour present to the mass of air present. With this metric, there are direct analogies between the conduction, convection, and advection modes of heat transport and mass transport (conduction of heat is equivalent to diffusion of mass). The analogies are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Analogy between heat transport and moisture transport.

	Heat transport	Moisture transport
Conduction (diffusion)	$\dot{q}'' = -k\nabla T$	$\dot{m}'' = -\rho_a D_v \nabla \omega$
Convection	$\dot{q}'' = h(T_w - T_\infty)$	$\dot{m}'' = K(\omega_w - \omega_\infty)$
Advection	$\dot{q} = \dot{m}_a c_p T$	$\dot{m} = \dot{m}_a \omega$

When building the solution matrix for the moisture problem, the moisture conductors are analogous to the thermal conductors in the thermal problem. For conduction (diffusion), the moisture conductor is defined as $C_{diff}^m = \rho_a D_v A / \Delta l$, where A is the cross-sectional area across which the moisture is diffusing, and Δl is the distance between the communicating moisture nodes. Alternatively, if an evaporative resistance across a fabric is known, a moisture conductor is the reciprocal of the resistance, modified by a scale factor to account for the driving potential to be humidity ratio instead of vapour pressure. Convection moisture conductors are defined as $C_{conv}^m = K_M A$. The m superscript indicates participation in the moisture transport problem.

The mass balance for a moisture node is expressed as

$$\epsilon \rho_a V \frac{d\omega_i}{dt} = \sum C_{diff_{ij}}^m (\omega_j - \omega_i) + \sum C_{conv_{ik}}^m (\omega_k - \omega_i) + \dot{m}_{imposed} \quad (1)$$

where ϵ is the porosity of the material associated with node i , ρ_a is the density of air, V is the volume associated with the node, ω_i is the humidity ratio at node i , and $\dot{m}_{imposed}$ is the imposed mass flow rate on the node, which could be a sweat rate at a skin layer.

Results and Discussion

The advanced clothing moisture model was tested by comparing its predictions to measurements derived from sweating hot plate experiments. A stack of 3 materials was considered: a Gore-tex® 3-layer laminate (GTX3L) outer layer, a Polyester lofted batting (PEB) middle layer, and a Capilene® base layer (CAP). The properties of the fabrics were measured independently and are provided in Table 2.

Table 2. Validation Test Case Fabric Properties.

Fabric	Thickness	Density	Specific Heat	Therm. Res.	Evap. Res.
Name	mm	kg/m ³	kJ/kg-K	m ² K/W	m ² Pa/W
Capilene (CAP)	0.636	250	0.935	0.011	4.28
Polyester lofted batting (PEB)	10.160	12.0	0.922	0.185	24.43
Gortex 3-layer laminate (GTX3L)	0.349	450	1.155	0.006	11.44

Type-K thermocouples were sewn into both surfaces of each individual fabric. Hot plate testing was executed under cool, humid ambient conditions (i.e., 2 °C and 80% RH) in order to promote condensation within the layered stack-up when the hot plate's sweating feature was activated. Temperature measurements and predictions for both the wet and dry conditions are presented in the graphs in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Comparison of Wet vs. Dry Fabric Temperatures. Top and bottom data point labels indicate the face closest to the hot plate (“btm”) and the face closest to the ambient conditions (“top”).

Conclusions

This study illustrates the importance of considering layer-to-layer vapour transport when modelling clothing. The model was able to reproduce the relatively significant rise in outer surface temperature seen in the measurements. The model predictions indicate that the rise in temperature was due to the thermal effect of condensation occurring within outer layers of the fabric stack.

References

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